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HIGH-PRECISION CALCULATION OF THE STRESS STATE OF THE REINFORCED LAYER ON TWO CYLINDRICAL SUPPORTS WITH SMOOTH CONTACT

Abstract.

The spatial problem of elasticity theory is solved for a layer containing cylindrical reinforcement and located on two cylindrical supports embedded in it. The supports are subjected to contact-type conditions (normal displacements and tangential stresses), which model a bearing. Stresses are set on the flat surfaces of the layer, and rigid conjugation conditions are set between the elastic cylindrical inclusion and the layer. The solution to the problem is based on the Lamé equation, to which the generalized Fourier method is applied. The numerical analysis of the stress state of the layer is carried out and compared with the work where other boundary conditions are set.

Keywords: layer with cylindrical cavities; generalized Fourier method; layer with cylindrical inclusions.

Introduction. Cylindrical bearing joints are common in the mechanical and aerospace industries. The accuracy of calculations of such joints is an important factor that affects the bearing life. Therefore, it is important to choose the method that most accurately determines the stress-strain state of the body.

Analytical methods [1 – 4] are accurate, but these methods do not allow obtaining the stress-strain state for a spatial body with more than three boundary surfaces. In this case, it is necessary to simplify the model or apply approximate methods.

Approximate (numerical) methods [5, 6] are more extensive. However, approximate methods do not always yield the required accuracy, especially for infinite elements.

Another approach is analytical and numerical methods, the accuracy of which depends on technical parameters (number of terms in the series, order of the system of equations, etc.). However, such methods also have limitations related to the shape of the body, physical and mechanical characteristics, the presence of stress concentrators, and the influence of external factors. For example, works [7, 8] solve problems for a layer with a stress concentrator located perpendicular to the boundaries of the layer and cannot take into account longitudinal elements.

For problems with longitudinal stress concentrators, the analytical and numerical generalized Fourier method is more suitable [9].

This method has been used to solve problems for a cylinder with cylindrical cavities or inclusions [10-12], for a half-space with a cylindrical cavity [13], for a layer with a single cylindrical cavity or inclusion [14, 15], and for a layer with several cavities or inclusions [16, 17].

The closest works are [18, 19], which solve problems for a layer with two cylindrical cavities and one cylindrical inclusion. Thus, in [18], the boundary conditions are considered in the form of given displacements on the surfaces of the cavities (a layer on embedded supports), in [19], non-proprietary mixed boundary conditions on the upper and lower boundaries of the layer, and stresses on the surfaces of the cavities. However, these works do not allow solving the problem with contact-type conditions, which additionally requires the separation of the Lamé equation and the orthogonal transition formula.

Therefore, there is a need to create a method for solving a similar problem, taking into account the conditions of the contact type on the surfaces of the cavities (which models the bearing connection).

The purpose of the paper is to:

3. Solving a problem similar to [18, 19], but with stresses given on the surface of the layer, on cylindrical surfaces of cavities - contact-type conditions.
4. Comparison of the results with [18] for analyzing the effect on the stress state of contact-type boundary conditions on a support instead of displacements.

Problem statement. In an elastic homogeneous layer there are N circular cylindrical inhomogeneities (two cavities and one inclusion) of radius R_p , where p is the number of cylinder, $p=1, 2, 3$.

Circular cylindrical inhomogeneities will be considered in local cylindrical coordinate systems (ρ_p, φ_p, z) , a layer in the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , which is equally oriented and combined with the inclusion coordinate system ($p=1$). The upper boundary of the layer is located at distance $y=h$, the lower boundary at distance $y=-\tilde{h}$. Find the solution to the Lamé equation, given the stresses at the boundaries of the layer:

$$F\vec{U}(x, z)|_{y=h} = \vec{F}_h^0(x, z),$$

$$F\vec{U}(x, z)|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = \vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z),$$

contact type conditions are set at the boundaries of cylindrical cavities ($p = 2, 3$)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_\rho(\varphi, z)|_{y=h} &= U_0^{(p)}(\varphi, z), \\ \tau_{\rho\varphi}|_{y=h} &= \tau_1^{(p)}(\varphi, z), \\ \tau_{\rho z}|_{y=h} &= \tau_2^{(p)}(\varphi, z) \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_h^0(x, z) &= \tau_{yx}^{(h)}\vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(h)}\vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(h)}\vec{e}_z, \\ \vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z) &= \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})}\vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})}\vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})}\vec{e}_z, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$U_0^{(p)}(\varphi, z), \tau_1^{(p)}(\varphi, z), \tau_2^{(p)}(\varphi, z)$ are known functions, which we will assume to be rapidly decreasing to zero at far distances from the origin in the z coordinate for cavity surfaces and in the x and z coordinates for layer boundaries.

Research Methodology. The basic solutions of the Lamé equation are as follows [9]

$$\vec{u}_k^\pm(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) = N_k^{(d)} e^{i(\lambda z + \mu x) \pm \gamma y};$$

$$\vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) = N_k^{(p)} I_m(\lambda \rho) e^{i(\lambda z + m\varphi)}; \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) = N_k^{(p)} \left[(\text{sign } \lambda)^m K_m(|\lambda| \rho) \cdot e^{i(\lambda z + m\varphi)} \right]; k = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$N_1^{(d)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla; N_2^{(d)} = \frac{4}{\lambda} (v - 1) \vec{e}_2^{(1)} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla(y \cdot); N_3^{(d)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(1)} \cdot); N_1^{(p)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla;$$

$$N_2^{(p)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left[\nabla \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + 4(v - 1) \left(\nabla - \vec{e}_3^{(2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \right]; \quad N_3^{(p)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(2)} \cdot);$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \mu^2}, \quad -\infty < \lambda, \mu < \infty,$$

where v is the Poisson's ratio; $I_m(x), K_m(x)$ are modified Bessel functions; $\vec{R}_{k,m}, \vec{S}_{k,m}, k=1, 2, 3$ are internal and external solutions of the Lamé equation for a cylinder, respectively; $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}, \vec{u}_k^{(+)}$ are solutions of the Lamé equation for a layer.

The solution to the problem is presented in the form [19].

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_0 &= \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(H_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) + \tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) \right) d\mu d\lambda + \\ &+ \sum_{p=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda) d\lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{U}_1 = \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} A_{k,m}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda) d\lambda,$$

where $\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ and $\vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda)$ are the basic solutions given by formulas (4), and the unknown functions $H_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $\tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda)$ and $A_{k,m}(\lambda)$ must be found from the boundary conditions.

Eighteen equations were written to find the unknowns: satisfaction of the boundary conditions at the upper boundary of the layer (three for each ordinate), at the lower boundary of the layer (three for each ordinate), six on the surfaces of cylinders $p = 2, p = 3$ (normal displacements and two tangential stresses), and two additional equations written as conjugation conditions between the layer and the inclusion ($p = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1} &= \vec{U}_1(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1}, \\ F\vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1} &= F\vec{U}_1(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1}. \end{aligned}$$

To satisfy the boundary conditions, functions (2) are previously represented by a double Fourier integral, functions (1) by an integral and a Fourier series. After that, the integrals and Fourier series are eliminated from the right and left sides of the resulting equations.

To write each equation in its own coordinate system, we used the formulas for the transition of basic solutions between coordinate systems [19].

After solving the system of equations, all unknown equations (4) are found.

To obtain numerical results, the systems of equations were solved by the truncation method in the parameter m .

Results and Discussion. In an elastic isotropic layer, two cylindrical cavities and a cylindrical inclusion are located parallel to its surfaces. The layer is plastic, Poisson's ratio $\nu_0 = 0.38$, elastic modulus $E_0 = 1.7 \cdot 10^3$ MPa, the inclusion is steel, Poisson's ratio $\nu_1 = 0.25$, elastic modulus $E_1 = 2 \cdot 10^5$ MPa.

Distance from the center of the inclusion to the upper and lower boundaries of the layer $h = \tilde{h} = 12$ mm. Radii of inhomogeneities $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = 5$ mm. Distance from the inclusion to the cavities $p = 2$ and $p = 3$: $L_{12} = L_{13} = 30$ mm, $\alpha_{12} = 0$, $\alpha_{13} = \pi$.

The stresses $\sigma_y^{(h)}(x, z) = -10^8 \cdot (z^2 + 10^2)^{-2} \cdot (x^2 + 10^2)^{-2}$, $\tau_{yx}^{(h)} = \tau_{yz}^{(h)} = 0$ are given on the upper surface of the layer. At the lower boundary of the layer, the stresses $\sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})}(x, z) = \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} = \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} = 0$ are given. On the surfaces of the cavities, normal displacements and tangential stresses are given $U_0^{(p)}(\varphi, z) = \tau_1^{(p)}(\varphi, z) = \tau_2^{(p)}(\varphi, z) = 0$.

The infinite system was reduced to $m = 4$. The accuracy of the boundary conditions at the specified values of the geometric parameters is 10^{-4} .

Changing the boundary conditions on the surfaces of the supports from displacements [18] to contact-type conditions changes the stress state of the layer at the reinforcement site.

The stresses σ_ρ on the mating surface in the body of the layer in comparison with [18] are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Stresses σ_ρ in the body of the layer at the interface; 1 - specified contact-type conditions; 2 - specified displacements.

Under the given contact-type boundary conditions on the supports (instead of displacements), the stresses σ_ρ (Fig. 1, line 1) increase slightly on the mating surface. This is a consequence of the absence of moments on the supports, which leads to an increase in stresses between the supports.

The stresses σ_φ in the body of the layer at the interface are shown in Fig. 2 in comparison with the variant when displacements are specified instead of contact-type conditions.

Fig. 2. Stresses σ_φ in the body of the layer at the interface; 1 - specified contact-type conditions; 2 - specified displacements.

In the case of the specified contact-type conditions, the maximum stresses σ_φ at the interface increase significantly (Fig. 2, line 1). Given the increase in stresses σ_φ with increasing distance between the supports [18], the total effect of these parameters can be critical.

The stresses σ_z in the body of the layer at the interface are shown in Fig. 3 also in comparison with the variant when displacements are specified instead of contact-type conditions.

Fig. 3. Stresses σ_z in the body of the layer at the interface; 1 - specified contact-type conditions; 2 - specified displacements.

As can be seen from Fig. 3, the stresses σ_z also increase when contact-type conditions are applied to the supports.

This indicates that when bearing connections are used, as well as in the event of a loss of rigidity at given displacements, stresses in the inter-bearing space increase significantly, overloading the connection in the reinforcement zone.

Changing the boundary conditions has almost no effect on the stress $\tau_{\rho\varphi}$ in the reinforcement zone. The stress plot $\tau_{\rho\varphi}$ almost coincides with [18].

Conclusions. A method for solving the spatial problem of elasticity theory for a layer located on two embedded supports (under the given conditions of smooth contact) and having a longitudinal cylindrical inclusion is

proposed. The problem is solved by means of the generalized Fourier method and reduced to an infinite system of linear algebraic equations, to which the method of reduction is applied.

The obtained highly accurate result made it possible to compare the variants of supports with smooth contact conditions and supports with specified displacements. The numerical analysis suggests that the presence of contact-type conditions significantly increases the stress state between the supports in the reinforcement zone.

The method can be applied to structures whose design scheme coincides with the formulation of the given problem.

Further research is relevant for replacing the full-body inclusion with a pipe.

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